

The Suśruta Project

The textual and cultural history of medicine in South Asia based on newly-discovered manuscript evidence

Menu

HOME PROJECT OVERVIEW ∨ PROJECT TEAM ∨ THE TOOLBOX ∨
THE LABORATORY ∨ PROJECT PUBLICATIONS TRAINING ∨

Menu

NAK 5/333 is not a direct copy of KL 699: further evidence

Posted on May 3, 2022 by Deepto Chakraborty

^[1]In his 2014 article, Kengo Harimoto determined that although the Nepalese manuscripts of the Suśrutasaṃhitā [KL 699 \(K\)](#), [NAK 1-1079 \(N\)](#) and [NAK 5-333 \(H\)](#) are closely related, none of them is a direct copy of another. ([Harimoto, 2014, 1089](#)). K and H are dated to 878 AD and 1543 AD respectively. Based on palaeographical traits, Harimoto opines that N is younger than K but older than H (op. cit. p. 1087). Nonetheless, N and H are more closely related to each other than to K.

Harimoto's arguments

To support the argument that none of these manuscripts is a direct descendant of another, Harimoto provides the following evidence from *Sūtrasthāna* 1.12 (op. cit. 1089):

K (2r1) reads : *suśruto bhagavantam prakṣyaty asyopadiśyamānaṃ*

K 2r1

N (1v7-2r1) and H (2v2-3) read: *suśruto bhagavantam pratyakṣasyopadiśyamāṇam*

N 1v7

N 2r1

H 2v2

H 2v3

K consists of the correct reading ...*prakṣyaty asyo*... while the conjunctive error of N and H suggest that N and H descend from a hyparchetype that is different from K.

As N is considered to be older than H, one can surmise that N was directly copied from K, and H was directly copied from N. But Harimoto gives another example, where the correct reading *ta ete* (*Sūtrasthāna* 1.26) is found in both K and H but N consists of a corrupt reading *ete* in which the pronoun *ta* (<*te*) is omitted. He, therefore, concludes that H was not copied from N. Another possibility, according to Harimoto, is that both N and H were copied from a hyparchetype which was a direct copy of K.

New evidence

Harimoto’s preliminary remarks are based on his examination of “a very limited portion of the Suśrutasaṃhitā” (op. cit. 1091). However, as we have already transcribed a great part of the text from all these three manuscripts we now have more evidence that backs Harimoto’s preliminary observations. In this blog post, I am giving a few more examples from the manuscripts K and H which suggest that the scribe of H did not have access to the manuscript K or at least to its main codicological unit. We, however, need to keep in mind that the codex K, as Klebanov points out, consists of at least four different codicological units. (Klebanov, 2021, 11). So, what is true for one codicological unit is not necessarily true for all others. However, the section examined here (*Uttaratantra* 18 and 19^[2]) belongs to the largest codicological unit of K which even consists of the final colophon of the manuscript (op. cit. 12-13).

In the following examples from *Uttaratantra* 18 and 19, the bold characters are omitted in H even though K contains them.

- *Uttaratantra* 18.28: *ekāhaṃ vā dvyaham vāpi (...kāham vā <space/>hañ caiṣāṃ* in H)

H 376v5

K 169r1

- *Uttaratantra* 18.45: *tau tu tridhā prayujyete rogeṣu puṭapākavat / (...prayuñjīta... in H)*

H 377r2

K 169r3

- *Uttaratantra* 18:64: *adaḥṣiṇaṃ daḥṣiṇena ḥṣipet kānīnam añjanaṃ* |

H 378r1

K 169v3

- *Uttaratantra* 18:83: *yuñjyād yathārtham etāni pṛthak pṛthag athāpi vā* // (yujyād... in H)

H 378v5

K 170r2

- *Uttaratantra* 18.97: *etad bhadrodayan nāma sadā vārhati bhūpatiḥ* | (... <space/> rddati bhūpatiḥ in H)

H 379r6

K 170r7

- *Uttaratantra* 19.4: *uktaṃ purā kṣatajapittajaśūlapathyam (uktā... in H)*

H 380r1

K 170v3

- *Uttaratantra* 19.9: *stanyapradoṣajanitaḥ (stanyapra<space/>yajanitaḥ in H)*

H 380r3

K 170v4

- *Uttaratantra* 19.16: *śukratadañjanan tu |*

H 380v3

K 171r1

Evidently, these are not examples of scribal errors because the scribe of H leaves space for the omitted characters. It is obvious that the manuscript or manuscripts that the scribe of H used for his copy consisted of either lacunae or glyphs illegible to the scribe in these places. These characters are quite clearly written in K. Therefore, H is not a direct copy of K.

Reference

Harimoto, Kengo. 2014. "Nepalese Manuscripts of the Suśrutasaṃhitā." *Journal of Indian and Buddhist Studies*, Vol. 62, No. 362 (3): 23--29 (1087-1093).

<https://www.academia.edu/6695321/>.

Klebanov, Andrey. 2021. "On the Textual History of the Suśrutasaṃhitā, (2): An Anonymous Commentary and Its Identified Citations." In *Body and Cosmos: Studies in Early Indian Medical and Astral Sciences in Honor of Kenneth G. Zysk*, 110--139.

Leiden, Boston: Brill. https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004438224_008.

Footnotes

- 1 I am thankful to Jason Birch for his valuable comments and suggestions about this blog post.

- 2 The chapter and verse numbers used here are according to the vulgate edition. Chapters 18 and 19 of the Uttaratāntra are actually chapters 17 and 18 respectively in the Nepalese manuscripts.

RECENT BLOG POSTS

[NAK 5/333 is not a direct copy of KL 699: further evidence](#)

[Long-term data security](#)

[Manuscripts beyond this project](#)

[On ambiguous nasals](#)

[Note to “Doṣas by the Numbers”](#)

CATEGORIES

Select Category ▼

ARCHIVES

[May 2022](#)

[April 2022](#)

[March 2022](#)

[January 2022](#)

[December 2021](#)

[October 2021](#)

[August 2021](#)

[July 2021](#)

[June 2021](#)

April 2021

March 2021

February 2021

January 2021

December 2020

October 2020

April 2020

The Suśruta Project is funded as a four-year Insight Grant by the Canadian Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council. Grant no. 435-2020-1077. Dates: 1 April 2020 - 31 March 2024. Application DOI.

Supplementary funding is provided for the project from the Singhmar Chair Endowment Grant administered by the University of Alberta.

This website and all files created by this project are copyrighted by Dominik Wujastyk and the Suśruta Project and distributed under a Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International License.

UNIVERSITY OF
ALBERTA

